

Unnecessary religious lockout: Comprehensive statistical results of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Christian Orthodox countries in Easter 2020.

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Abstract

A huge experiment, on a multinational and intercontinental level, was conducted in Eurasia in Holy Week 2020 as to what extent COVID-19 is transmitted among worshipers in Easter liturgies in Orthodox Christian countries. The experiment involved all Orthodox countries in Eastern Europe and the Caucasus. The set of Orthodox countries was in effect divided into two statistical subsets: on the one hand, countries where their citizens were allowed to attend Easter liturgies (like Georgia, Bulgaria etc.), and on the other, countries where a state ban was imposed on any presence of the faithful in Christian temples during Holy Week (like Greece, Russia etc.). In that dichotomic religious context, an unanticipated phenomenon was recorded statistically: More than a month after the Resurrection, the deaths from COVID-19 in the former countries were on average and proportionally less than such deaths in the latter countries. It is noteworthy that Georgia's performance in curbing the coronavirus pandemic in Spring 2020 has evolved to a paradigm in the Orthodox world: As of May 15, 2020, new coronavirus deaths in Georgia were zero (0) every day until Ascension Day, as result of Georgia's measured anti-pandemic policies that took into due consideration both medical suggestions and religious traditions in Holy Week. In this context, the statistical findings in this monograph might be useful for the effective and measured management of the pandemic in Easter, according to the successfully applied model of Georgia: In sum, it has been statistically established that attendance in Orthodox liturgies of the Holy Passions does not contribute, in and by itself, to the spread of COVID-19, as long as basic safety precautions are taken by the church and duly observed by the faithful.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic; lockdown; Orthodox liturgy; Holy Communion; World Health Organization; WHO; Central and Eastern Europe; Greece; Georgia.

Introduction

A de facto experiment of historical significance was conducted in Eurasia in Holy Week 2020, as to whether and to what extent COVID-19 is transmitted among worshipers in Easter liturgies in Orthodox Christian countries. The experiment was huge, on a multinational and intercontinental level, as it involved all Orthodox countries in Eastern Europe and the Caucasus, i.e. the countries where the Orthodox constitute the majority of the population.

The set of these (12) countries, with total population of 256 million, was in effect divided into two statistical subsets: on the one hand, (5) countries that allowed their citizens to attend liturgies and receive the Holy Communion during Holy Week, and on the other, (7) countries that imposed a religious lockout [As regards to official re-

strictions to religious practices in Holy Week in 2000, the term “lockout” is more accurate than the term “lockdown”: In several Orthodox countries, priests were then allowed to conduct liturgies (i.e. the temples were not closed down) but without the presence of the faithful (who were thus kept out of the temples)] or even a draconian ban [indicatively, as to the draconian degree to which the religious lockout was sometimes enforced, priests were arrested, charged and fined in several parts of Greece in Spring 2020 for “holding mass behind closed doors” or for “offering Communion to a congregation” either inside or outside (at the doorstep of) a temple; moreover, even “worshipers were arrested for violating the [religious-lockout] order” (1,2)] on any presence of the faithful in Christian temples during Holy Week. In that dichotomic religious context—with similar or same conditions (*ceteris paribus*) as to socio-economic horizontal lockdown, and about the same starting point of pandemic-deaths dynamics, [with respect to statistical methodology, the de facto experiment in the Orthodox countries in Holy Week 2020 was in effect carried out under ideal analytical conditions: The dichotomy of the Orthodox countries—between two statistically distinct groups, i.e. lockout countries and non-lockout countries—took

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place in similar or same conditions of other factors that might affect the evolution of the pandemic in the two subsets. Indicatively: (a) At the beginning of Holy Week, both homodox subsets were at about the same starting point of COVID-19 death rate, i.e. cumulative total of 2.65 (3.42) deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants on average in lockout (non-lockout) countries [Table 1, column 14, last two lines, where these numbers are rounded up to the next integer, i.e. 3 (4)]. (b) In all (12) Orthodox countries, an almost identical universal lockdown (social, economic, educational), that aimed to curb the pandemic, was in full force at the time. (c) The Orthodox countries have similar traditions and value systems, due to which no Orthodox country had implemented policies of “herd immunization” against the pandemic at the time. (d) Most Orthodox countries are genetically related, having population of Slavic descent or with considerable Slavic admixtures] in either group of countries at the beginning of Easter 2020—an unanticipated phenomenon was recorded quantitatively, i.e. statistically: More than a month after the Resurrection, and in contrast to pertinent epidemiological predictions or even warnings, the deaths from COVID-19 in the (5) Orthodox countries that allowed participation of the faithful in Easter liturgies were on average and proportionally (per 1,000,000 people) less than such deaths in the (7) Orthodox countries that imposed a horizontal religious lockout in the same period; less deaths, not more.

Testing of hypothesis

In particular, the Orthodox countries that explicitly or implicitly allowed worshipers to attend liturgies during Holy Week were the following five, with total population of 66 million: Belarus, Bulgaria, Georgia, the Republic of North Macedonia and Ukraine—colored in green, in the table entitled “COVID-19 cases and deaths in Christian Orthodox countries, April 12 to May 28, 2020” (Table 1). The Orthodox countries of religious lockout were the following seven, with total population of 190 million: Cyprus, Greece, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Russia, Serbia (colored in brown in the table).

In the (7) Orthodox countries where religious lockout was imposed, a statistical hypothesis prevailed that if no lockout was effected during Holy Week, then deaths from the coronavirus in every such country would soon, within 1-2 months thereafter, reach levels similar to those of Italy at the time, [indicatively, even in Orthodox Georgia, where worshipers were allowed to attend the Holy Passions during the COVID-19 pandemic, Professor Paata Imnadze, Scientific Director of the National Center for Disease Control and Public Health (NCDC) in Georgia, urged Christians to “stay home, or what happened to Italy will happen to us” (3). In Orthodox Greece, where worshipers were officially forbidden from attending liturgies in Holy Week, the Greek government's conjectural (statistically unsubstantiated) argumentation—which was widely propagated by mainstream media, that were financed by the Greek state with about \$25,000,000 to promote the governmental agenda on the pandemic at the time—pertained

to the following two arguments: (a) Churches are “health bombs” ready to “explode” in Easter celebrations (4); (b) given that “saliva is one of the means of transmission” of viruses (5), the particular virus (COVID-19) is assumedly transmitted through the Holy Communion; therefore the faithful “should avoid receiving the Holy Communion until we have a safe vaccine” (6). Those contentions, though, were in historical contrast to the undisputed fact that the Holy Communion has never been associated conclusively with a pandemic outbreak in the two-millennium history of Orthodoxy (7) i.e. of the order of hundreds of such deaths per month per 1,000,000 inhabitants in the country. [An implied milder version of that null hypothesis was that in Orthodox countries where believers were allowed to attend liturgies during Holy Week, COVID-19 deaths would surpass by far those in Orthodox countries where religious lockout was imposed—e.g. with more deaths of the order of tens per month per 1,000,000 inhabitants]. In particular, Italy was then cited as an anti-paradigm, to be avoided at all costs (socioeconomic, political, psychological, etc.), given that 18,641 such deaths had been recorded from March 11 to April 11 in Italy that year (2020), or equivalently 308 deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants during the 31-day period preceding Holy Week in that (Catholic) country.

The testing of that (null) hypothesis, as well as of similar hypotheses in favor of religious lockout in Orthodox countries, is now possible on the basis of the final statistical data on the performance of Orthodox countries, as regards the evolution of the pandemic in Eastern Europe and the Caucasian region. In particular, on the basis of cumulative data of the World Health Organization (WHO), it has been established [the proof method in this study is deterministic rather than stochastic, i.e. without posing question of distribution functions or of statistical-sample validity, because the relevant data (Table 1) are ex post results—not ex ante—of the performance of all Orthodox countries as to their entire population, in all their regions, without possible fluctuations in the values of the variables. Therefore the conclusions drawn herein are deductive rather than inductive, e.g. as applies to final results of national elections and not to (probabilistic) estimates of pre-election polls] that all those hypothetical assumptions and (rather conjectural) predictions did not reflect reality at all: In the 46-day period from Palm Sunday to Ascension Day (April 12 to May 28), i.e. until 39 days after Easter Sunday [the incubation period of COVID-19 is 3-14 days (8) and the median hospitalization period (LoS) of patients with coronavirus ranges from 4 to 21 days in countries outside China (9). Therefore, the 39-day period from Easter Sunday to Ascension Day (April 19 - May 28) is sufficient in order for epidemiologists to draw reasonably sound conclusions about the spread of COVID-19 during Holy Week (April 12-19) in Orthodox countries in 2020, the deaths from COVID-19 in the (5) Orthodox countries, where the faithful were allowed to participate in the Holy Passions, amounted to 15 deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants on average (Table 1, column 16, penultimate line), while in the (7) homodox countries, where

religious lockdown was enforced, such deaths were almost twice as much proportionally, i.e. they amounted to 29 deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants on average (Table 1, column 16, last line). Therefore it has been proved conclusively that in the (5) Orthodox countries where the faithful participated in the Holy Passions, such deaths not only did they not amount to hundreds per 1,000,000 inhabitants [In general, in the 46-day period from Palm Sunday to Ascension Day in 2020, the COVID-19 death toll in Orthodox countries was of the order of tens per 1,000,000 inhabitants in the worst cases, and in no case of the order of hundreds (Table 1, column 16): In that period, Moldova and Romania had the worst performances (67 and 48 such deaths respectively) although they both imposed religious lockdown, while Georgia performed best (only 3 such deaths) although it did not impose such lockdown] (as happened in some heterodox Christian countries, like Italy etc.), but in fact they were proportionally even less than the corresponding (almost double) deaths in the homodox countries that enforced religious lockdown upon the population. Therefore, as derived conclusively [In the 46-day period from Palm Sunday to Ascension Day (April 12 to May 28) in 2020, the cumulative total of deaths from COVID-19 in the (7) Orthodox countries where religious lockdown was enforced increased by 839% (from 650 to 6,101 deaths in total, or equivalently from 4 to 33 deaths per million people), while the corresponding cumulative total in the homodox countries that did not impose religious lockdown increased by considerably (33%) less, i.e. by 560% (from 175 to 1,155 in total, or equivalently from 3 to 18 deaths per million people) (Table 1, columns 11-16, last two lines). As to the cumulative total of COVID-19 cases, the performance of each group of countries was of the same order in that period: It increased by 1.286% (from 30,381 to 421,038 cases in total, or equivalently from 160 to 2,214 cases per million people) in the lockdown country group, while it increased by little (6%) more, i.e. by 1.364% (from 4,615 to 67,532 cases in total, or equivalently from 70 to 1,020 cases per million people) in the non-lockout country group (Table 1, columns 4-9, last two lines). To the extent that COVID-19 deaths (not cases) are the bottom line, the most important criterion, in appraising the effectiveness of anti-pandemic policies, and in view of the statistical evidence that (a) the two groups of Orthodox countries differed considerably as to pandemic-deaths dynamics, while (b) their performance was more or less similar (of the same order) as to pandemic-cases dynamics at the same time, the statistical evidence for the rejection of the null hypothesis is obviously conclusive.] from real outcomes—in an exact test, which involves complete ex post (deterministic, not probabilistic) enumeration of all outcomes—the epidemiological null hypothesis is rejected, because the (assumed) high transmissibility of COVID-19 in Easter liturgies in Orthodox countries was not corroborated by factual data. On the other hand, on the basis of the same statistical data, the following alternative hypothesis, that was expressed explicitly and ex ante (before Easter) by numerous Orthodox priests in Eastern Europe, is accepted: Provided that all worshippers observe

elementary safety precautions—like face-mask wearing and social distancing, both inside and in the vicinity of temples, hand disinfection, natural ventilation of the temples by keeping both main-entrance and side doors open during liturgies, etc.—the participation of the faithful in the Holy Passions not only does it not cause a drastic increase in coronavirus deaths, but on the contrary contributes therapeutically [In the present context, the meaning of “therapeutical” relates to “strengthening a believer's immune system” rather than “helping cure a disease”. Any such strengthening might be conducive to curbing the pandemic, in light of the much better performance of countries with no lockout, comparatively to that of countries with lockout, in Orthodox Eurasia in Holy Week (Table 1). In general, such therapeutical effect might be attributed partially to the impact of religious beliefs and practices (“belief systems”) on health, and especially on the immune system of many (though not all) believers (10, 11,12) to stemming the pandemic in Holy Week.

Inconclusive explanation of the phenomenon

One of the reasons that the coronavirus was not transmitted among the faithful in Orthodox liturgies in Holy Week of 2020, in contrast to what took place then in some heterodox churches around the world, might partially be attributed to the Orthodox rite, in which neither a large choir exists nor the faithful participate actively in group hymnology (both of which are characteristic of heterodox, not Orthodox, liturgies). [Heterodox multi-member choirs may act as “superspreaders” of the virus, as “scientists have traced other outbreaks to a funeral, [non-Orthodox] church service, and rowdy bar, all involving enthusiastic group singing” (13). For example, the virus was transmitted to 45 members of the 121-member Choir of the Skagit Valley County during an afternoon rehearsal at the Presbyterian Church in Mount Vernon, Washington (14). Similarly, “a religious group in South Korea has been identified as a coronavirus hotbed” (15): At Jesus Shincheonji Church in Daegu, South Korea, “one person is thought to have transmitted the virus to hundreds in this way” (16). On the contrary, in Orthodox countries in Easter 2020, not even one Orthodox temple, not even one Orthodox liturgy, was recorded as an actual “superspreader” of COVID-19]. Moreover the difference in COVID-19 transmission between Orthodox and non-Orthodox countries might also be partially due to universal TB-vaccination policies in most Orthodox countries (17,18,19).

But even if these explanations as to the difference in coronavirus transmissibility in Orthodox countries vis-à-vis heterodox countries are valid, they still do not explain the paradox of the (better) performance of Orthodox countries that allowed the faithful to participate in liturgies in Holy Week, in comparison to the (worse) performance of Orthodox countries that imposed religious lockdown at the time. The explanation of the phenomenon may be amenable to further research and academic debate, but the existence of the phenomenon per se is indisputable, in light of the comprehensive and conclusive statistical data (Table 1).

Therefore, despite the inconclusiveness as to the explanation of the phenomenon, the faith of Orthodox believers might rather be strengthened by those statistical findings, because they have disproved conclusively, and quite undisputably, [Policy tool. On June 2, 2020, the statistical findings, including the prime table (Table 1), of this monograph were submitted to the office of the Prime Minister of Greece and therefrom to Greek epidemiologists, who had already advised the government to impose a draconian religious lockout in the country as of March 16, 2020. At the same time, a first draft of this report in Greek, including the table in English, was also sent via e-mail to all (400+) Orthodox Archdioceses around the world. The statistical validity of the table (based on pertinent data of WHO) has not been disputed by anyone, including top epidemiologists and councilors of the Greek Government, or any other government, ever since. As result, the table (although not formally published in a journal at the time) effected a noticeable change in ecclesiastical anti-pandemic policies in Greece and other Orthodox countries: As of next month (July 2020), liturgy attendance of the faithful has been allowed in Orthodox churches, under the proviso that basic precautions—like safe distancing, mask wearing, hand disinfection etc.—are orderly and willingly observed by liturgy participants, per the paradigm of Georgia. In sum, as regards the Orthodox Church and governments of Orthodox countries, the table has evolved to a policy tool for pandemic crisis management as of June 2020] the (hypothetical) necessity of religious lockout in Orthodox countries in Holy Week.

The Georgian paradigm of measure in the pandemic

Georgia's performance in curbing the coronavirus pandemic in Spring 2020 has emerged as a most effective (top) paradigm in the Orthodox world, and beyond: Georgians attended Holy Passions orderly [the disciplined attendance of Georgian Orthodox faithful in Holy-Week liturgies, is depicted on the two chart-background photographs, taken by Nino Alavidze / Agenda.ge (Figure 1) and Mariam Nikuradge / OC Media (Figure 1) in the Holy Trinity Cathedral in Tbilisi, Georgia, in Easter 2020] and with spectacular results: During the 46-day period from Palm Sunday to Ascension Day, only nine (9) deaths in total took place in Georgia, i.e. only three (3) deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants respectively (Table 1, first line, columns 13 and 16 respectively). Furthermore, as of May 15, 2020, new coronavirus deaths in Georgia were zero (0) every day until Ascension Day (28 May 2020). [As to the better performance of Georgia (that did not impose religious lockout) in comparison to that of Greece (that imposed religious lockout), in the 38-day period from April 20 to May 28, 2020, i.e. from Monday of Renewal Week (right after Easter Sunday) until Ascension Day, a total of 61 COVID-19 deaths were recorded in Greece against only 8 such deaths in Georgia, i.e. nearly 6 deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants in Greece versus only 2 deaths per 1,000,000 inhabitants in Georgia (Tables 2-3). In addition to that fact—i.e. after Easter Sunday, coronavirus new deaths in Greece were proportionally almost three times higher than those in Georgia—it is noteworthy that Georgia (but not Greece) managed to eliminate the number of COVID-19 new deaths in the middle of that period, i.e. about two weeks before Ascension Day (Table 3 and Figure 2): From 15 May 2020 until the end of the period and beyond

(the end of May 2020), the number of COVID-19 new deaths per day in Georgia was zero (0)]. Georgia's success in Easter 2020 did not come about by chance. [In a press conference (Oct 2, 2016), His Holiness Pope Francis stated: "I had two surprises in Georgia. One is Georgia itself. I never imagined so much culture, so much faith, so much Christianity. They are a people of believers with a very ancient Christian culture, a people of many martyrs. I also discovered something I did not know: the deep roots of this Georgian faith. The second surprise was the Patriarch. He is a man of God; this man moved me. The times that I met him, I came away deeply moved, and with the feeling of having found a man of God. Truly, a man of God" (20)]. The Government of Georgia did not "blindly" (one-dimensionally) adopt the recommendations of epidemiologists: "Contrary to medical advice, religious gatherings were not restricted by law largely to ensure that the Georgian Orthodox Church could conduct liturgies for Orthodox Easter" (Agenda, 18 April 2020). In particular, Georgia laid out and implemented, with measure a "golden ratio" or "balance" between medical (material) suggestions and religious (spiritual) traditions—measure (μέτρον) is the fundamental concept of Classical Civilization (21)—with the quantifiable result that, according to Prime Minister Giorgi Gakharia, "the Georgian people have managed to both show a high sense of social responsibility and remain devoted to their faith and the church" (22).

Conclusion

The statistical findings [Methodologically, this monograph gives emphasis in reporting COVID-19 cases and deaths per million people (Table 1, columns 7-9 and 14-16), in line with the standard analytical methodology of WHO and pertinent bibliography. To this end, population estimates per specific date (Table 4, columns 5-7) are derived from UN population estimates (officially shared by WHO) for 2019-2020 (Table 4, columns 2-4).

More analytically, the UN has specified mid-year population estimates for the years 2019 and 2020 for every country, i.e. as of 7-1-2019 and 7-1-2020 correspondingly (Table 4, columns 2 and 3 correspondingly). These estimates imply an annual growth rate (r_i) of the population for every country (i) in 2019-2020 (Table 4, column 4). On the basis of that rate, the population, $P_i(\text{date})$, of a country (i) at a specific date (date) within that period, is specified as $P_i(\text{date}) = P_i(\text{date}_0) * (1 + r_i / 366) d(\text{date})$, where $\text{date}_0 = "7-1-2019"$, and $d(\text{date})$ is the number of days from date_0 until the date (Table 4, columns 5-7)] in this monograph are useful for the effective and measured management of the next COVID-19 waves in 2021-2022 according to the successfully applied model of Georgia in Easter 2020. In sum, it has been statistically established that attendance in Orthodox liturgies of the Holy Passions does not contribute, in and by itself, to the spread of COVID-19, as long as basic safety precautions are duly observed. [Those governments in Central and Eastern Europe that have been attempting "to control the narrative of the COVID-19 pandemic and restrict the media under the guise of public health" (23), can barely attribute the second and third waves of the pandemic (24) to orderly Orthodox congregations:

In light of the findings of this report (Table 1), the reasons of those waves should rather be searched for elsewhere—not in Orthodox churches—i.e. in (a) “underfunded health-care systems” and understaffed hospitals, (b) lack of “an effective test and trace system” in the region, (c) government inconsistencies “in imposing and enforcing lockdowns,” (d) belated government reactions “to soaring infection rates,” (e) the comparatively “higher proportion of multi-generation households and the large share of jobs in big factories” in Central and Eastern Europe, as “compared to Western Europe,” (f) administrative failures “to roll out vaccinations, even when they have enough vaccine doses to do so,” and so on (25). As to the third wave, the negative impact of these factors was greatly compounded by “EU’s failure to deliver COVID-19 vaccines at pace” (26).

Table 1. COVID-19 cases and deaths in Christian Orthodox countries, April 12 to May 28, 2020

COVID-19 cases and deaths in **Christian Orthodox countries**,¹ April 12 to May 28, 2020

RANK <small>(countries ordered by column 16)</small>	COUNTRY <small>(1)</small>	POPULATION ²		CASES						DEATHS					
		as of 12 Apr 2020 <small>(2)</small>	as of 28 May 2020 <small>(3)</small>	absolute numbers			per million people			absolute numbers			per million people		
				cumulative total		Difference between 12-Apr and 28-May <small>(6)</small>	cumulative total ³		Difference between 12-Apr and 28-May <small>(9)</small>	cumulative total		Difference between 12-Apr and 28-May <small>(13)</small>	cumulative total ³		Difference between 12-Apr and 28-May <small>(16)</small>
				12-Apr (Palm Sunday) <small>(4)</small>	28-May (Ascension Day) <small>(5)</small>		12-Apr (Palm Sunday) <small>(7)</small>	28-May (Ascension Day) <small>(8)</small>		12-Apr (Palm Sunday) <small>(11)</small>	28-May (Ascension Day) <small>(12)</small>		12-Apr (Palm Sunday) <small>(14)</small>	28-May (Ascension Day) <small>(15)</small>	
1	Georgia	3,990,838	3,989,886	257	738	481	65	185	120	3	12	9	1	4	3
2	Cyprus	1,205,460	1,206,571	633	941	308	526	781	255	11	17	6	10	15	5
3	Greece	10,434,145	10,427,837	2,114	2,906	792	203	279	76	98	175	77	10	17	7
4	Montenegro	628,046	628,055	272	324	52	434	516	82	3	9	6	5	15	10
5	Ukraine	43,791,031	43,758,530	277	22,382	22,105	7	512	505	83	669	586	2	16	14
6	Bulgaria	6,959,855	6,953,401	675	2,477	1,802	97	356	259	29	134	105	5	20	15
7	Serbia	8,745,031	8,740,665	3,630	11,300	7,670	416	1,293	877	80	241	161	10	28	18
8	Belarus	9,449,998	9,449,610	2,578	39,858	37,280	273	4,218	3,945	26	219	193	3	24	21
9	Russian Federation	145,920,872	145,928,693	15,770	379,051	363,281	109	2,598	2,489	130	4,142	4,012	1	29	28
10	North Macedonia	2,083,393	2,083,382	828	2,077	1,249	398	997	599	34	121	87	17	59	42
11	Romania	19,265,667	19,249,809	6,300	18,791	12,491	328	976	648	316	1,235	919	17	65	48
12	Moldova	4,036,001	4,034,835	1,662	7,725	6,063	412	1,915	1,503	12	282	270	3	70	67
COUNTRY GROUP TOTALS	All countries	256,510,337	256,451,274	34,996	488,570	453,574	137	1,906	1,769	825	7,256	6,431	4	29	25
	Countries with churches open in Easter	66,275,115	66,234,809	4,615	67,532	62,917	70	1,020	950	175	1,155	980	3	18	15
	Countries with churches closed in Easter	190,235,222	190,216,465	30,381	421,038	390,657	160	2,214	2,054	650	6,101	5,451	4	33	29

SOURCE: United Nations Organization (UNO); World Health Organization (WHO): "World Health Statistics 2021".

Table 1

¹ In green (brown), countries with Christian Orthodox churches open (closed) to worshippers in Easter.

² Population estimates were derived from UN/WHO data for 2019-2020, as specified in Table 4.

³ Decimal numbers are rounded up to the next integer, e.g. 0.75 → 1; 2.64 → 3; 3.42 → 4.

Table 2. COVID-19 PRE-Easter Statistics of Greece and Georgia (2020)

COVID-19 Pre-Easter Statistics of Greece and Georgia (2020)

Day seq. #	Date	GREECE							GEORGIA						
		Population ¹	Cases			Deaths			Population ¹	Cases			Deaths		
			new	total	per million people	new	total	per million people		new	total	per million people	new	total	per million people
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)
1	26-Feb-20	10,440,457	1	1	0.1				3,991,790	1	1	0.3			
2	27-Feb-20	10,440,320	2	3	0.3				3,991,769	0	1	0.3			
3	28-Feb-20	10,440,183	1	4	0.4				3,991,749	1	2	0.6			
4	29-Feb-20	10,440,046	3	7	0.7				3,991,728	1	3	0.8			
5	1-Mar-20	10,439,908	0	7	0.7				3,991,707	0	3	0.8			
6	2-Mar-20	10,439,771	0	7	0.7				3,991,686	0	3	0.8			
7	3-Mar-20	10,439,634	0	7	0.7				3,991,666	0	3	0.8			
8	4-Mar-20	10,439,497	2	9	0.9				3,991,645	0	3	0.8			
9	5-Mar-20	10,439,359	22	31	3.0				3,991,624	6	9	2.3			
10	6-Mar-20	10,439,222	14	45	4.4				3,991,604	0	9	2.3			
11	7-Mar-20	10,439,085	21	66	6.4				3,991,583	4	13	3.3			
12	8-Mar-20	10,438,948	7	73	7.0				3,991,562	0	13	3.3			
13	9-Mar-20	10,438,810	11	84	8.1				3,991,542	2	15	3.8			
14	10-Mar-20	10,438,673	5	89	8.6				3,991,521	8	23	5.8			
15	11-Mar-20	10,438,536	10	99	9.5				3,991,500	1	24	6.1			
16	12-Mar-20	10,438,399	18	117	11.3	1	1	0.1	3,991,479	1	25	6.3			
17	13-Mar-20	10,438,261	73	190	18.3	0	1	0.1	3,991,459	0	25	6.3			
18	14-Mar-20	10,438,124	38	228	21.9	2	3	0.3	3,991,438	5	30	7.6			
19	15-Mar-20	10,437,987	103	331	31.8	1	4	0.4	3,991,417	3	33	8.3			
20	16-Mar-20	10,437,850	21	352	33.8	0	4	0.4	3,991,397	0	33	8.3			
21	17-Mar-20	10,437,712	35	387	37.1	1	5	0.5	3,991,376	1	34	8.6			
22	18-Mar-20	10,437,575	31	418	40.1	0	5	0.5	3,991,355	4	38	9.6			
23	19-Mar-20	10,437,438	46	464	44.5	1	6	0.6	3,991,335	2	40	10.1			
24	20-Mar-20	10,437,301	31	495	47.5	4	10	1.0	3,991,314	4	44	11.1			
25	21-Mar-20	10,437,164	35	530	50.8	3	13	1.3	3,991,293	5	49	12.3			
26	22-Mar-20	10,437,026	94	624	59.8	2	15	1.5	3,991,272	5	54	13.6			
27	23-Mar-20	10,436,889	71	695	66.6	2	17	1.7	3,991,252	7	61	15.3			
28	24-Mar-20	10,436,752	48	743	71.2	3	20	2.0	3,991,231	9	70	17.6			
29	25-Mar-20	10,436,615	78	821	78.7	2	22	2.2	3,991,210	5	75	18.8			
30	26-Mar-20	10,436,477	71	892	85.5	5	27	2.6	3,991,190	4	79	19.8			
31	27-Mar-20	10,436,340	74	966	92.6	1	28	2.7	3,991,169	4	83	20.8			
32	28-Mar-20	10,436,203	95	1061	101.7	4	32	3.1	3,991,148	7	90	22.6			
33	29-Mar-20	10,436,066	95	1156	110.8	7	39	3.8	3,991,128	1	91	22.9			
34	30-Mar-20	10,435,929	56	1212	116.2	7	46	4.5	3,991,107	12	103	25.9			
35	31-Mar-20	10,435,791	102	1314	126.0	3	49	4.7	3,991,086	7	110	27.6			
36	1-Apr-20	10,435,654	101	1415	135.6	2	51	4.9	3,991,065	7	117	29.4			
37	2-Apr-20	10,435,517	129	1544	148.0	2	53	5.1	3,991,045	17	134	33.6			
38	3-Apr-20	10,435,380	69	1613	154.6	10	63	6.1	3,991,024	21	155	38.9			
39	4-Apr-20	10,435,243	60	1673	160.4	5	68	6.6	3,991,003	7	162	40.6	1	1	0.3
40	5-Apr-20	10,435,105	62	1735	166.3	5	73	7.0	3,990,983	12	174	43.6	1	2	0.6
41	6-Apr-20	10,434,968	20	1755	168.2	6	79	7.6	3,990,962	14	188	47.2	0	2	0.6
42	7-Apr-20	10,434,831	77	1832	175.6	2	81	7.8	3,990,941	8	196	49.2	1	3	0.8
43	8-Apr-20	10,434,694	52	1884	180.6	2	83	8.0	3,990,921	15	211	52.9	0	3	0.8
44	9-Apr-20	10,434,557	71	1955	187.4	4	87	8.4	3,990,900	7	218	54.7	0	3	0.8
45	10-Apr-20	10,434,420	56	2011	192.8	5	92	8.9	3,990,879	16	234	58.7	0	3	0.8
46	11-Apr-20	10,434,282	70	2081	199.5	1	93	9.0	3,990,858	8	242	60.7	0	3	0.8

SOURCE: United Nations Organization (UNO); World Health Organization (WHO): "World Health Statistics 2021".

Table 2

¹ Population estimates were derived from UN/WHO data for 2019-2020, as specified in Table 4.

² Decimal numbers are rounded up to the first decimal digit, e.g. 0.095 → 0.1; 0.287 → 0.3; 2.969 → 3.0.

Table 3. COVID-19 Easter Statistics of Greece and Georgia (2020)

Day seq. #	Date	GREECE							GEORGIA						
		Population ¹	Cases			Deaths			Population ¹	Cases			Deaths		
			new	total	per million people	new	total	per million people		new	total	per million people	new	total	per million people
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)
47	12-Apr-20	10,434,145	33	2,114	202.7	5	98	9.4	3,990,838	15	257	64.4	0	3	0.8
48	13-Apr-20	10,434,008	31	2,145	205.6	1	99	9.5	3,990,817	15	272	68.2	0	3	0.8
49	14-Apr-20	10,433,871	25	2,170	208.0	2	101	9.7	3,990,796	28	300	75.2	0	3	0.8
50	15-Apr-20	10,433,734	22	2,192	210.1	1	102	9.8	3,990,776	6	306	76.7	0	3	0.8
51	16-Apr-20	10,433,597	15	2,207	211.6	3	105	10.1	3,990,755	42	348	87.3	0	3	0.8
52	17-Apr-20	10,433,459	17	2,224	213.2	3	108	10.4	3,990,734	22	370	92.8	0	3	0.8
53	18-Apr-20	10,433,322	11	2,235	214.3	2	110	10.6	3,990,714	18	388	97.3	1	4	1.1
54	19-Apr-20	10,433,185	0	2,235	214.3	4	114	11	3,990,693	6	394	98.8	0	4	1.1
55	20-Apr-20	10,433,048	10	2,245	215.2	2	116	11.2	3,990,672	8	402	100.8	0	4	1.1
56	21-Apr-20	10,432,911	156	2,401	230.2	5	121	11.6	3,990,651	6	408	102.3	0	4	1.1
57	22-Apr-20	10,432,774	7	2,408	230.9	0	121	11.6	3,990,631	8	416	104.3	1	5	1.3
58	23-Apr-20	10,432,636	55	2,463	236.1	4	125	12	3,990,610	9	425	106.6	0	5	1.3
59	24-Apr-20	10,432,499	27	2,490	238.7	5	130	12.5	3,990,589	19	444	111.3	0	5	1.3
60	25-Apr-20	10,432,362	16	2,506	240.3	0	130	12.5	3,990,569	12	456	114.3	0	5	1.3
61	26-Apr-20	10,432,225	11	2,517	241.3	4	134	12.9	3,990,548	30	486	121.8	1	6	1.6
62	27-Apr-20	10,432,088	17	2,534	243.0	2	136	13.1	3,990,527	11	497	124.6	0	6	1.6
63	28-Apr-20	10,431,951	32	2,566	246.0	2	138	13.3	3,990,507	14	511	128.1	0	6	1.6
64	29-Apr-20	10,431,813	10	2,576	247.0	1	139	13.4	3,990,486	6	517	129.6	0	6	1.6
65	30-Apr-20	10,431,676	15	2,591	248.4	1	140	13.5	3,990,465	22	539	135.1	0	6	1.6
66	1-May-20	10,431,539	21	2,612	250.4	0	140	13.5	3,990,444	27	566	141.9	1	7	1.8
67	2-May-20	10,431,402	8	2,620	251.2	3	143	13.8	3,990,424	16	582	145.9	1	8	2.1
68	3-May-20	10,431,265	6	2,626	251.8	1	144	13.9	3,990,403	7	589	147.7	1	9	2.3
69	4-May-20	10,431,128	6	2,632	252.4	2	146	14	3,990,382	4	593	148.7	0	9	2.3
70	5-May-20	10,430,991	10	2,642	253.3	0	146	14	3,990,362	11	604	151.4	0	9	2.3
71	6-May-20	10,430,853	21	2,663	255.4	1	147	14.1	3,990,341	6	610	152.9	0	9	2.3
72	7-May-20	10,430,716	15	2,678	256.8	1	148	14.2	3,990,320	5	615	154.2	0	9	2.3
73	8-May-20	10,430,579	13	2,691	258.0	2	150	14.4	3,990,300	8	623	156.2	1	10	2.6
74	9-May-20	10,430,442	19	2,710	259.9	1	151	14.5	3,990,279	3	626	156.9	0	10	2.6
75	10-May-20	10,430,305	6	2,716	260.4	0	151	14.5	3,990,258	9	635	159.2	0	10	2.6
76	11-May-20	10,430,168	10	2,726	261.4	0	151	14.5	3,990,238	3	638	159.9	1	11	2.8
77	12-May-20	10,430,031	18	2,744	263.1	1	152	14.6	3,990,217	4	642	160.9	0	11	2.8
78	13-May-20	10,429,894	16	2,760	264.7	3	155	14.9	3,990,196	5	647	162.2	0	11	2.8
79	14-May-20	10,429,756	10	2,770	265.6	1	156	15	3,990,175	20	667	167.2	1	12	3.1
80	15-May-20	10,429,619	40	2,810	269.5	4	160	15.4	3,990,155	4	671	168.2	0	12	3.1
81	16-May-20	10,429,482	9	2,819	270.3	2	162	15.6	3,990,134	12	683	171.2	0	12	3.1
82	17-May-20	10,429,345	15	2,834	271.8	1	163	15.7	3,990,113	12	695	174.2	0	12	3.1
83	18-May-20	10,429,208	2	2,836	272.0	2	165	15.9	3,990,093	6	701	175.7	0	12	3.1
84	19-May-20	10,429,071	4	2,840	272.4	0	165	15.9	3,990,072	6	707	177.2	0	12	3.1
85	20-May-20	10,428,934	10	2,850	273.3	1	166	16	3,990,051	6	713	178.7	0	12	3.1
86	21-May-20	10,428,797	3	2,853	273.6	2	168	16.2	3,990,031	8	721	180.8	0	12	3.1
87	22-May-20	10,428,660	21	2,874	275.6	1	169	16.3	3,990,010	2	723	181.3	0	12	3.1
88	23-May-20	10,428,522	2	2,876	275.8	2	171	16.4	3,989,989	5	728	182.5	0	12	3.1
89	24-May-20	10,428,385	2	2,878	276.0	0	171	16.4	3,989,968	2	730	183.0	0	12	3.1
90	25-May-20	10,428,248	4	2,882	276.4	1	172	16.5	3,989,948	1	731	183.3	0	12	3.1
91	26-May-20	10,428,111	10	2,892	277.4	1	173	16.6	3,989,927	1	732	183.5	0	12	3.1
92	27-May-20	10,427,974	11	2,903	278.4	0	173	16.6	3,989,906	3	735	184.3	0	12	3.1
93	28-May-20	10,427,837	3	2,906	278.7	2	175	16.8	3,989,886	3	738	185.0	0	12	3.1

SOURCE: United Nations Organization (UNO); World Health Organization (WHO): "World Health Statistics 2021".

Table 3

¹ Population estimates were derived from UN/WHO data for 2019-2020, as specified in Table 4.

² Decimal numbers are rounded up to the first decimal digit, e.g. 0.751 → 0.9; 1.002 → 1.1; 2.756 → 2.8.

Table 3. Population of Christian Orthodox countries, 2019-2020

Population of Christian Orthodox countries, 2019-2020

COUNTRY (in alphabetical order)	UN/WHO population data			Population estimates (derived form UN/WHO population data, i.e. from columns 2-4)		
	Population		annual growth rate mid 2019 to mid 2020	as of 2/26/2020	as of 4/12/2020	as of 5/28/2020
	as of 7/1/2019	as of 7/1/2020				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Belarus	9,452,409	9,449,323	-0.03265%	9,450,386	9,449,998	9,449,610
Bulgaria	7,000,117	6,948,445	-0.73816%	6,966,315	6,959,855	6,953,401
Cyprus ¹	1,198,574	1,207,361	0.73312%	1,204,350	1,205,460	1,206,571
Georgia ²	3,996,762	3,989,175	-0.18983%	3,991,790	3,990,838	3,989,886
Greece	10,473,452	10,423,056	-0.48118%	10,440,457	10,434,145	10,427,837
Moldova ³	4,043,258	4,033,963	-0.22989%	4,037,167	4,036,001	4,034,835
Montenegro	627,988	628,062	0.01178%	628,037	628,046	628,055
North Macedonia	2,083,459	2,083,374	-0.00408%	2,083,403	2,083,393	2,083,382
Romania	19,364,558	19,237,682	-0.65520%	19,281,538	19,265,667	19,249,809
Russian Federation	145,872,260	145,934,460	0.04264%	145,913,053	145,920,872	145,928,693
Serbia ⁴	8,772,228	8,737,370	-0.39737%	8,749,400	8,745,031	8,740,665
Ukraine ⁵	43,993,643	43,733,759	-0.59073%	43,823,556	43,791,031	43,758,530

SOURCE: United Nations Organization (UNO); World Health Organization (WHO): "World Health Statistics 2021".

Table 4

¹ Refers to the whole country.

² Including Abkhazia and South Ossetia.

³ Including the Transnistria region.

⁴ Including Kosovo.

⁵ Including Crimea.

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